

Extended Data for Franceschi & Volz, 2024.

Phylogenetic signatures reveal multilevel selection and fitness costs in SARS-CoV-2

Table of contents

Supplementary text	2
Extended Data Figures	3
Fig. S1. Frequency of identified TFP-homoplasies alongside the Spike protein for different lineages and cluster threshold = 2% between June 2020 and April 2022 (including Omicron) (A) employing the simple 99% frequency quantile method of artifact removal. (B) after removing all sequences having at least one of eight BA.1-spike defining mutations that were in the top100 of most frequent homoplasies.	4
Fig. S2. Frequency of identified synonymous TFP-homoplasies across all 10 cluster thresholds along the whole SARS-CoV-2 genome between June 2020 and April 2022 (including Omicron) on the first (lower) cluster threshold satisfied. (A) TFP-homoplasias colored by major PANGO-lineage. (B) TFP-homoplasias colored by the first threshold where identified.	5
Fig S3. False discovery rate (FDR) and ϵ statistic per genomic region for the 10 different cluster thresholds.	6
Fig. S4. Boxplot showing the distribution of mlscluster statistics across different cluster thresholds for a subset of clades detected by at least one statistic (union). A: Ratio of sizes. B: Ratio of persistence time. C: Logistic growth rate.	7
Fig. S5. TFP-homoplasia identification compared to positive selection method and across different major lineages. A: Comparison of top 30 identified sites under multilevel selection by our tree-based clustering approach for the period preceding Omicron (June 2020 to mid-November 2021) for cluster threshold = 2% against the HyPhy analysis (Pond 2022), also presenting concordant results (intersection) between both methods. B: Lineage-stratified sites under transient selection with bubble sizes representing frequencies.	8
Fig. S6. Bubble plot of AY.4.*-associated TFP-homoplasies extracted from a subset of top 30 more frequent TFPs across all lineages from June 2020 to April 2022 (including Omicron). The threshold where each identified mutated site was detected firstly is presented along the horizontal axis and colored by detection by mlscluster only or both HyPhy and mlscluster (intersection).	9
Fig. S7. Bubble plot of B.1.1.7-associated TFP-homoplasies extracted from a subset of top 30 more frequent TFPs across all lineages from June 2020 to April 2022 (including Omicron). The threshold where each identified mutated site was detected firstly is presented along the horizontal axis and colored by detection by mlscluster only or the intersection between methods.	10
Fig. S8. Bubble plot of AY.*(non-AY.4.*)-associated TFP-homoplasies extracted from a subset of top 30 more frequent TFPs across all lineages from June 2020 to April 2022 (including Omicron). The threshold where each identified mutated site was detected firstly is presented along the horizontal axis and colored by detection by mlscluster only or the intersection between methods.	11
Fig. S9. Bubble plot of BA.1.*-associated TFP-homoplasies extracted from a subset of top 30 more frequent TFPs across all lineages from June 2020 to April 2022 (including Omicron). The threshold where each identified mutated site was detected firstly is presented along the horizontal axis and colored by detection by mlscluster only or the intersection between methods.	12
Fig S10. Bubble plot of BA.2.*-associated TFP-homoplasies extracted from a subset of top 30 more frequent TFPs across all lineages from June 2020 to April 2022 (including Omicron). The threshold where each identified mutated site was detected firstly is presented along the horizontal axis and colored by detection by mlscluster only or the intersection between methods.	13
Fig S11. Frequency of identified TFP-homoplasies alongside other genomic regions with high	

normalised counts for cluster threshold = 2% and period including Omicron. (A) ORF7A. (B) ORF8. TFPs are coloured by major PANGO-lineage and annotated if frequency > 2. 14

Fig S12. Comparison of identified TFPs against fitness effects given by deep mutational scanning (DMS) experiments targeting the (A) spike protein (1) and (B) the RBD (2). TFPs that have positive and negative fitness effects estimated by DMS are shown. 15

Fig. S13. Comparison of identified TFPs against fitness effects given by the computational method described in Bloom & Neher (3). Distribution of (A) positive and (B) negative fitness effects across TFPs and non-TFPs over the entire SARS-CoV-2 genome. Segregated view of overlapping fitness categories across the (C) spike, (D) nucleocapsid and (E) ORF3A genes (the same genes shown in Fig. 5). TFPs that have positive and negative fitness effects as estimated by the compared method are shown. 16

Extended Data Table 17

Table S1. Top 100 TFP-homoplasies across all SARS-CoV-2 genomic regions identified for the period between June 2020 and April 2022 (including Omicron) and cluster threshold = 2%. Spike (S) mutations are marked in bold, and TFPs with frequency ≥ 5 are accompanied by their global and lineage distributions (from outbreak.info, last accessed 10 November 2023) and potential functional impact described in the literature. 17

References 26

Supplementary text

Text S1. Since the analysed clades and their defining homoplasies are selected from the subset of clades for which the specified cluster threshold was satisfied for at least one (union) of the three statistics, some variability in the distribution of the ratio of sizes and persistence times, as well as growth rates (see Methods: Tree-based clustering algorithm implementation), outside the cutoff points is expected. This occurs because not all the clades considered will be necessarily inside the thresholds for all three statistics. This behavior is intentionally less stringent to allow the inclusion of more potential sites under multilevel selection based on different evolutionary patterns. Intuitively, our results show that the range of the distribution of `mlscluster` statistics increases when cluster thresholds are increased, and this is more noticeable for the logistic growth rate statistic (Fig. S4).

Extended Data Figures

Fig. S2. Frequency of identified synonymous TFP-homoplasies across all 10 cluster thresholds along the whole SARS-CoV-2 genome between June 2020 and April 2022 (including Omicron) on the first (lower) cluster threshold satisfied. (A) TFP-homoplastic mutations colored by major PANGO-lineage. (B) TFP-homoplasies colored by the first threshold where identified.

Fig S3. False discovery rate (FDR) and ϵ statistic per genomic region for the 10 different cluster thresholds.

Fig. S4. Boxplot showing the distribution of `mlscluster` statistics across different cluster thresholds for a subset of clades detected by at least one statistic (union). A: Ratio of sizes. B: Ratio of persistence time. C: Logistic growth rate.

Fig. S6. Bubble plot of AY.4.*-associated TFP-homoplasies extracted from a subset of top 30 more frequent TFPs across all lineages from June 2020 to April 2022 (including Omicron). The threshold where each identified mutated site was detected firstly is presented along the horizontal axis and colored by detection by `mlscluster` only or both HyPhy and `mlscluster` (intersection).

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Fig. S8. Bubble plot of AY.*(non-AY.4.*)-associated TFP-homoplasias extracted from a subset of top 30 more frequent TFPs across all lineages from June 2020 to April 2022 (including Omicron). The threshold where each identified mutated site was detected firstly is presented along the horizontal axis and colored by detection by `mlcluster` only or the intersection between methods.

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Fig S10. Bubble plot of BA.2.*-associated TFP-homoplasies extracted from a subset of top 30 more frequent TFPs across all lineages from June 2020 to April 2022 (including Omicron). The threshold where each identified mutated site was detected firstly is presented along the horizontal axis and colored by detection by `mlscluster` only or the intersection between methods.

Fig S11. Frequency of identified TFP-homoplasies alongside other genomic regions with high normalised counts for cluster threshold = 2% and period including Omicron. (A) ORF7A. (B) ORF8. TFPs are coloured by major PANGO-lineage and annotated if frequency > 2.

Fig. S13. Comparison of identified TFPs against fitness effects given by the computational method described in Bloom & Neher (3). Distribution of (A) positive and (B) negative fitness effects across TFPs and non-TFPs over the entire SARS-CoV-2 genome. Segregated view of overlapping fitness categories across the (C) spike, (D) nucleocapsid and (E) ORF3A genes (the same genes shown in Fig. 5). TFPs that have positive and negative fitness effects as estimated by the compared method are shown.

Extended Data Table

Table S1. Top 100 TFP-homoplasies across all SARS-CoV-2 genomic regions identified for the period between June 2020 and April 2022 (including Omicron) and cluster threshold = 2%. Spike (S) mutations are marked in bold, and TFPs with frequency ≥ 5 are accompanied by their global and lineage distributions (from outbreak.info, last accessed 10 November 2023) and potential functional impact described in the literature.

Homoplasy	Frequency identified as defining mutation	Major lineage	Independently found under positive selection	Detailed genomic region	Amino acid length of mutated protein	Global and lineage distribution	Outbreak info link	Potential functional impact
ORF3A:L15F	14	B.1.1.7	0	ORF3A	275	>51 thousand sequences worldwide (<0.5%). Very common in low prevalence B.1.1.* lineages, but also detected in <1% frequencies in XBB.*, BQ.*, BA.2.*, BA.5.*, and AY*. Reached a maximum global prevalence of ~3% in early 2021.	Link	Unclear functional impact. ORF3A probably plays a role, in conjunction with other proteins, on the viral life cycle during viral entry through endocytosis, endomembrane-associated viral transcription and replication, and viral release through exocytosis (4).
ORF1AB:G519S	9	Other	0	NSP2	638	>125 thousand sequences worldwide (1%). Not initially associated with VOCs, oscillated in frequency reaching a peak of ~2% globally by the end of 2021, declined, and then by early 2023 resurged in XBB variants (but only reaching ~3% prevalence).	Link	Unclear functional impact.
ORF8:Y73C	8	B.1.1.7	0	ORF8	121	>1.1 million sequences worldwide (8%). Alpha defining mutation that reached predominance (~60%) especially in the UK between early and mid-2021, subsequently appearing in low proportions on BA and AY backgrounds.	Link	This mutation is localized at a noncovalent dimer interface responsible for the formation of ORF8 protein complexes, which may enable viral evasion from host immune responses. ORF8 is proposed to interfere with immune responses, including the disruption of IFN-I signaling and downregulation of MHC-I (5).
ORF1AB:H5264Y	7	AY.4.*	0	NSP12	932	>2 thousand sequences worldwide (<0.5%). Very low frequencies during the pandemic (always <0.5%), appearing in the background of	Link	Unclear functional impact.

ORF1AB:K3353R	7	B.1.1.7	0	NSP5	306	<p><0.5% AY.4 and more recently XBB sequences.</p> <p>>205 thousand sequences worldwide (1%). Firstly noticed as Beta defining mutation, subsequently appeared in the background of other VOCs (especially Delta, but also BA and XBB) reaching a maximum global prevalence of ~4% between mid-2020 and mid-2021.</p>	Link	Unclear functional impact.
ORF1AB:R7014N	7	AY.4.*	0	NSP16	298	<p>>45 thousand sequences worldwide (<0.5%). Presented some oscillations of frequency not above 2% when surging at lower proportions in different lineages, especially AY and BA.1/XBB</p>	Link	Creates a consensus upstream transcription regulatory sequence (TRS-B) that encodes a short transframe peptide (nsp16.iORF), whose resulting sub-genomic mRNAs were found to be expressed during human infection (6).
ORF3A:P240S	7	AY.4.*	0	ORF3A	275	<p>>32 thousand sequences worldwide (<0.5%). Appeared in ~1% Alpha sequences and have oscillated its frequency between 0 and 0.5% during the pandemic appearing in the background of Beta, Gamma, BA, AY, and XBB lineages</p>	Link	Unclear functional impact.
ORF1AB:P309L	6	BA.2.*	0	NSP2	638	<p>>136 thousand sequences worldwide (1%). Reached a peak in prevalence of ~6% during the AY.4 wave by mid-2021, also detected later in low prevalence (<1%) in BA/XBB lineages.</p>	Link	Unclear functional impact.
ORF1AB:T2274I	6	AY.4.*	0	NSP3	1945	<p>>27 thousand sequences worldwide (<0.5%). Achieved the highest point in prevalence at 4% in mid-2020 in B.1 lineages, later identified in low frequencies in AY.4 and BA lineages.</p>	Link	Unclear functional impact.
ORF3A:S171L	6	B.1.1.7	0	ORF3A	275	<p>>81 thousand sequences worldwide (<0.5%). Defining mutation of the Beta variant, reached a maximum global prevalence ~3%. Also displayed next to zero frequency but was consistently detected in the background of other VOCs.</p>	Link	Lead to alterations in the secondary structure and increased protein disorder of the ORF3a protein (7).

S:A688V	6	Other	0	S:FCS	38	>36 thousand sequences worldwide (<0.5%). Its frequency oscillated between 0 and 1% during the pandemic, after appearing in the background of major VOCs	Link	Unclear functional impact.
S:L216F	6	AY.4.*	0	S:NTD	292	>12 thousand sequences worldwide (<0.5%). Detected in lower frequencies on AY and BA/XBB-related variants.	Link	Infectivity of a pseudovirus construct with this mutation in the background of B.1.1.7 (alpha) was two times higher than that of D614G, but it was not associated with escape to monoclonal antibodies (8).
S:S98F	6	BA.1.*	0	S:NTD	292	>53 thousand sequences worldwide (<0.5%). Detected in lower frequencies on B.1.177 and Alpha (reaching a maximum of ~3% prevalence), and later on BA/XBB-related lineages.	Link	Increased the infectivity of SARS-CoV-2 in animal models (9).
N:P151L	5	BA.1.*	0	N	413	>27 thousand sequences worldwide (<0.5%). Firstly reached a global prevalence of ~10% by mid-2020 in the B.1.1.284 lineage, and later remained circulating at <1% prevalence in multiple BA and AY lineages.	Link	Unclear functional impact. The primary function of N protein involves recognizing and encapsulating the viral RNA within a symmetrical helical arrangement, serving a crucial and diverse role throughout the coronavirus life cycle (e.g., mRNA transcription and replication, and immune regulation) (10).
ORF1AB:A2994V	5	Other	0	NSP4	500	>20 thousand sequences worldwide (<0.5%). Reached a maximum global prevalence of ~2% in B.1.1-derived lineages and later appeared in very small frequencies (<1%).	Link	Unclear functional impact.
ORF1AB:K322R	5	B.1.1.7	0	NSP2	638	>10 thousand sequences worldwide (<0.5%). Identified in BA and AY lineages at lower (<0.5%) frequencies and reached maximum prevalence on XBB-derived lineages in early 2023 (~0.5%).	Link	Unclear functional impact.
ORF1AB:L6924F	5	BA.1.*	0	NSP16	298	>19 thousand sequences worldwide (<0.5%). Detected in <2% frequency during the pandemic in the background of Alpha, AY, and BA/XBB lineages.	Link	Unclear functional impact.

ORF1AB:P7013L	5	AY.4.*	0	NSP16	298	>26 thousand sequences worldwide (<0.5%). As ORF1AB:L6924F, identified in <2% frequency during the pandemic in the background of Alpha, AY, and BA/XBB lineages.	Link	Associated with an intra-host micro-evolutionary event in a long-term (7 months) asymptomatic SARS-CoV-2 carrier, whose infection was sustained by multiple viral subpopulations (11).
ORF1AB:S5674L	5	AY.4.*	0	NSP13	601	>36 thousand sequences worldwide (<0.5%). Independently acquired by Alpha, AY, and BA/XBB lineages, later peaked by mid-2022 in the background of BA.5 at 2% frequency worldwide.	Link	Unclear functional impact.
ORF1AB:T1822I	5	BA.1.*	0	NSP3	1945	>92 thousand sequences worldwide (1%). Reached a global peak at 3% during the BA.1 wave and dropped to continue below 1% in subsequent BA/XBB lineages.	Link	Unclear functional impact.
ORF1AB:T5941I	5	AY.* (non-AY.4.*)	0	NSP14	527	>78 thousand sequences worldwide (1%). Peaked globally in prevalence around mid-2021 during the AY waves, but also appeared in BA/XBB lineages later on.	Link	Unclear functional impact.
ORF3A:D155Y	5	AY.* (non-AY.4.*)	0	ORF3A	275	>111 thousand sequences worldwide (1%). First detected consistently in Gamma sublineages, also presented <2% frequency during the pandemic being consistently detected in the background of other VOCs (especially AY.4 and BA.1).	Link	Reduce the ORF3a binding affinity to human caveolin-1 protein, potentially avoiding cell apoptosis and extending the asymptomatic phase of infection (12).
ORF3A:L106F	5	B.1.1.7	0	ORF3A	275	>271 thousand sequences worldwide (2%). First detected in Alpha at lower frequencies, reached >10% frequency during the BA.1 wave (early 2022), and dropped quickly a few months later. Also present in the background of other VOCs.	Link	Unclear functional impact.
S:A67V	5	B.1.1.7	1	S:NTD	292	>2.4 million sequences worldwide (16%). Earlier identified in Delta AY lineages in lower proportions, then reached predominance during the global BA.1 wave (early 2022) as its defining mutation and rapidly dropped a few months later.	Link	Unclear functional impact.

S:E484K	5	B.1.1.7	1	S:RBD	223	>263 thousand sequences worldwide (2%). Predominantly detected as defining mutation of Beta and Gamma variants (early 2021, ~15% prevalence worldwide) that did not outcompeted Alpha and Delta in the UK. Later detected in low frequencies in Alpha, Delta AY and Omicron BA lineages	Link	Increases the binding affinity with hACE2 (13). Reduces the neutralization by antibodies in the sera (14–16). Immune evasive against >10 monoclonal antibodies (17). Within-host antigenic drift in an immunosuppressed patient with low titers of neutralizing antibodies led to the emergence of both E484K and N501Y mutations (18).
M:L34F	4	AY.4.*	0	M	222			
N:D63G	4	AY.4.*	0	N	413			
ORF1AB:A1049V	4	B.1.177.*	0	NSP3	1945			
ORF1AB:A5922V	4	AY.4.*	0	NSP13	601			
ORF1AB:A6044V	4	AY.* (non-AY.4.*)	0	NSP14	527			
ORF1AB:D5584Y	4	AY.4.*	0	NSP13	601			
ORF1AB:G6173V	4	AY.4.*	0	NSP14	527			
ORF1AB:H1108Y	4	AY.* (non-AY.4.*)	0	NSP3	1945			
ORF1AB:L681F	4	AY.4.*	0	NSP2	638			
ORF1AB:M5997I	4	AY.* (non-AY.4.*)	0	NSP14	527			
ORF1AB:P1640S	4	B.1.1.7	0	NSP3	1945			
ORF1AB:P1803S	4	BA.1.*	0	NSP3	1945			
ORF1AB:P4619L	4	AY.4.*	0	NSP12	932			
ORF1AB:P6932S	4	B.1.177.*	0	NSP16	298			
ORF1AB:R3164H	4	AY.4.*	0	NSP4	500			
ORF1AB:R5716C	4	B.1.1.7	0	NSP13	601			
ORF1AB:S1188L	4	AY.4.*	0	NSP3	1945			
ORF1AB:T1589I	4	AY.4.*	0	NSP3	1945			
ORF1AB:T5805M	4	BA.2.*	0	NSP13	601			

ORF1AB:T6833I	4	AY.* (non-AY.4.*)	0	NSP16	298
ORF1AB:T814I	4	AY.* (non-AY.4.*)	0	NSP2	638
ORF3A:A110S	4	AY.* (non-AY.4.*)	0	ORF3A	275
ORF3A:P267L	4	AY.4.*	0	ORF3A	275
ORF7A:P34L	4	AY.4.*	0	ORF7A	121
ORF8:A65V	4	BA.2.*	0	ORF8	121
ORF8:L118V	4	B.1.1.7	0	ORF8	121
S:H49Y	4	AY.* (non-AY.4.*)	0	S:NTD	292
S:K444R	4	AY.4.*	0	S:RBD	223
E:V62F	3	Other	0	E	75
N:A152S	3	Other	0	N	413
N:A308S	3	B.1.1.7	0	N	413
N:H300Y	3	BA.2.*	0	N	413
N:P13L	3	AY.4.*	1	N	413
N:T379I	3	AY.4.*	0	N	413
ORF1AB:A138V	3	AY.4.*	0	NSP1	180
ORF1AB:A2891V	3	AY.* (non-AY.4.*)	0	NSP4	500
ORF1AB:A3357V	3	B.1.177.*	0	NSP5	306
ORF1AB:A5620S	3	B.1.1.7	0	NSP13	601
ORF1AB:A6285V	3	BA.1.*	0	NSP14	527
ORF1AB:D5130Y	3	BA.2.*	0	NSP12	932
ORF1AB:D5271Y	3	AY.* (non-AY.4.*)	0	NSP12	932
ORF1AB:E36D	3	AY.* (non-AY.4.*)	0	NSP1	180

ORF1AB:E5665D	3	AY.* (non-AY.4.*)	0	NSP13	601
ORF1AB:G442D	3	AY.* (non-AY.4.*)	0	NSP2	638
ORF1AB:H110Y	3	AY.4.*	0	NSP1	180
ORF1AB:H1160Y	3	Other	0	NSP3	1945
ORF1AB:K6958R	3	AY.4.*	0	NSP16	298
ORF1AB:L3086F	3	AY.4.*	0	NSP4	500
ORF1AB:L3829F	3	BA.1.*	0	NSP6	290
ORF1AB:M4993I	3	AY.* (non-AY.4.*)	0	NSP12	932
ORF1AB:P2018S	3	BA.1.*	0	NSP3	1945
ORF1AB:P4715L	3	AY.4.*	1	NSP12	932
ORF1AB:P6065S	3	B.1.177.*	0	NSP14	527
ORF1AB:P6128L	3	AY.4.*	0	NSP14	527
ORF1AB:P6128S	3	BA.1.*	0	NSP14	527
ORF1AB:P892S	3	B.1.177.*	0	NSP3	1945
ORF1AB:P943S	3	AY.* (non-AY.4.*)	0	NSP3	1945
ORF1AB:P971L	3	B.1.1.7	0	NSP3	1945
ORF1AB:P971S	3	AY.4.*	0	NSP3	1945
ORF1AB:R184C	3	BA.2.*	0	NSP2	638
ORF1AB:R7014C	3	AY.* (non-AY.4.*)	0	NSP16	298
ORF1AB:S135R	3	BA.2.*	0	NSP1	180
ORF1AB:S2114F	3	BA.1.*	0	NSP3	1945
ORF1AB:S2661F	3	B.1.1.7	0	NSP3	1945
ORF1AB:S3195G	3	AY.* (non-AY.4.*)	0	NSP4	500
ORF1AB:S4999I	3	AY.4.*	0	NSP12	932

ORF1AB:S944L	3	B.1.1.7	0	NSP3	1945
ORF1AB:T1521I	3	B.1.1.7	0	NSP3	1945
ORF1AB:T1543I	3	AY.4.*	0	NSP3	1945
ORF1AB:T2124I	3	AY.* (non-AY.4.*)	0	NSP3	1945
ORF1AB:T2424I	3	AY.4.*	0	NSP3	1945
ORF1AB:T3356I	3	B.1.1.7	0	NSP5	306
ORF1AB:T4477I	3	AY.4.*	0	NSP12	932
ORF1AB:T5262I	3	AY.4.*	0	NSP12	932
ORF1AB:T5563I	3	AY.4.*	0	NSP13	601
ORF1AB:T5912I	3	AY.4.*	0	NSP13	601
ORF1AB:T6566M	3	AY.4.*	0	NSP15	346
ORF1AB:V3595A	3	BA.1.*	0	NSP6	290
ORF3A:A103S	3	AY.4.*	0	ORF3A	275
ORF3A:G49V	3	AY.* (non-AY.4.*)	0	ORF3A	275
ORF3A:H78Y	3	B.1.1.7	0	ORF3A	275
ORF3A:T175I	3	B.1.1.7	0	ORF3A	275
ORF3A:T223I	3	AY.4.*	0	ORF3A	275
ORF3A:V202L	3	Other	0	ORF3A	275
ORF3A:W131C	3	AY.4.*	0	ORF3A	275
ORF6:R20S	3	AY.4.*	0	ORF6	61
ORF7A:A105V	3	AY.4.*	0	ORF7A	121
ORF7A:A55S	3	AY.* (non-AY.4.*)	0	ORF7A	121
ORF7A:H47Y	3	AY.* (non-AY.4.*)	0	ORF7A	121
ORF7A:P34S	3	AY.* (non-AY.4.*)	0	ORF7A	121

ORF7A:R78C	3	B.1.1.7	0	ORF7A	121
ORF8:V62L	3	AY.4.*	0	ORF8	121
S:A1022S	3	AY.* (non-AY.4.*)	0	S	721
S:A222V	3	BA.1.*	0	S:NTD	292
S:A701V	3	B.1.1.7	0	S:FCS	38
S:A879S	3	Other	0	S	721
S:A892V	3	AY.* (non-AY.4.*)	0	S	721
S:D574Y	3	AY.* (non-AY.4.*)	0	S	721
S:K1191N	3	AY.4.*	0	S	721
S:L938F	3	B.1.1.7	0	S	721
S:P1162L	3	AY.* (non-AY.4.*)	0	S	721
S:Q677H	3	AY.4.*	0	S:FCS	38
S:R273S	3	AY.4.*	0	S:NTD	292
S:R765L	3	BA.1.*	0	S	721
S:S704L	3	BA.2.*	0	S:FCS	38
S:S813I	3	AY.4.*	0	S	721
S:T33I	3	B.1.1.7	0	S:NTD	292
S:T51I	3	B.1.177.*	0	S:NTD	292
S:T572I	3	AY.4.*	0	S	721
S:T95I	3	AY.* (non-AY.4.*)	1	S:NTD	292
S:V1228L	3	AY.4.*	0	S	721
S:V1264L	3	AY.4.*	0	S	721

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